

Design of Surface Based Water Treatment Plant for Namobuddha Municipality

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Accepted July 06,2021
Published July 12,2021

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5092071>

Pages: 27-48

Funding: None

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How to cite this article (APA):
Adhikari, A., Dotel, S., & Baral, P. (2021). Design of Surface Based Water Treatment Plant for Namobuddha Municipality. *North American Academic Research*, 4(3), 27-48.
doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5092071>

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

The study is conducted for the calculation of a separate unit for the Water Treatment plant in Namobudhha Municipality. Detailed design and calculation of Treatment plant using Roshi river as the source is presented in this study. This study has calculated the water demand and designed different chemical, physical and chemical units. The objective of this work is to present design steps and calculations for the required units of a WTP. The design of the WTP units was applied to Roshi River water for the Namobuddha Municipality. The units of the treatment processes involved intake, coagulation, flocculation, sedimentation, filtration, disinfection, storage, and pumping. The water treatment plant was made for average discharge and the average population of 0.004 m³/sec and 32000 respectively. Besides, the calculation required some of the parameters to be estimated as all the required data are assumed with the references alongside. The outline results of each unit of the WTP were tabulated. It can be concluded that this work can be used as a source for designing other WTP units. Several factors such as the age of WTP, maintenance, economic and political situations, technical problems, and water demand had a great impact on the removal efficiency of the WTP units.

Keywords: WASTE WATER TREATMENT PLANT, SURFACE WATER

1. Introduction

Humanity faces numerous environmental problems due to increasing contaminants from point and non-point sources. Some of these compounds are toxic even at trace concentrations, especially when present as components of complex mixtures (Schwarzenbach et al. 2006). The demand for acceptable quality water increases with the population inflation and related activities including agriculture and manufacturing (Mahdizadeh Khasraghi et al. 2015). Most water in Earth's atmosphere and the crust comes from saline seawater, while freshwater accounts for nearly 1% of the total. The vast bulk of the water on Earth is saline or saltwater, with an average salinity of 35‰ (or 4.5%, roughly equivalent to 34 grams of salts in 1kg of seawater), though this varies slightly according to the amount of runoff received from surrounding land. In all, water from oceans and marginal seas, saline groundwater, and water from saline closed lakes amount to over 97% of the water on Earth, though no closed lake stores a globally

significant amount of water. Saline groundwater is seldom considered except when evaluating water quality in arid regions.

The remainder of Earth's water constitutes the planet's freshwater resource. Typically, freshwater is defined as water with a salinity of less than 1 percent that of the oceans i.e., below around 0.35%. Water with a salinity between this level and 1% is typically referred to as marginal water because it is marginal for many uses by humans and animals. The ratio of saltwater to fresh water on Earth is around 50 to 1.

The World Health Organization had done some arrangements to enhance the capacity of the water treatments plant by establishing the stations in the form of the story to exploit the area, establishing the internal walls of the basins of the treatment where algae can't growth (Mohammed & Shakir, 2012). Safe drinking water is water with microbial chemical and physical characteristics that meet WHO guidelines or national standards on drinking water quality (Oyebode et al., 2015). Seasonal events such a spring runoff, summer and fall algae blooms, and soil erosion affect final effluent quality. It was indicated that influent turbidity to the water plant is high during rainy periods.

Moreover, rivers are more susceptible to pathogen contamination than lakes and reservoirs, besides higher particulate concentrations. It was found that the watercolor highly affects the sizing of the particles and Giardia cysts as measured by the particle counter. The level of pathogens, such as Giardia and Cryptosporidium, in the filtered water, is related to their respective levels in raw water (Mohammed & Shakir, 2012)

1.1 Surface Water

Surface water is water located on top of the Earth's surface such as rivers, creeks, and wetlands. This may also be referred to as blue water. The vast majority is produced by precipitation and water runoff from nearby areas. As the climate gets warms in the spring, snowmelt runs off towards nearby streams and rivers contributing to a large portion of our drinking water. Levels of surface water lessen as a result of evaporation as well as water moving into the ground becoming groundwater. Alongside being used for drinking water, surface water is also used for irrigation, wastewater treatment, livestock, industrial uses, hydropower, and recreation. It is recorded by the Environmental Protection Act (EPA), that approximately 68 percent of water provided to communities comes from surface water. For USGS water-use reports, surface water is considered freshwater when it contains less than 1,000 milligrams per liter (mg/L) of dissolved solids.

The quality of surface water is governed by the content of living organisms and by the amounts of mineral and organic matter which it may have picked up in the course of its formation. As rain falls through the atmosphere, it collects dust and absorbs oxygen and carbon dioxide from the air. While flowing over the ground, surface water collects silt and particles of organic matter, some of which will ultimately go into solution. It also picks up more carbon dioxide from the vegetation and micro-organisms and bacteria from the topsoil and decaying matter. On inhabited watersheds, pollution may include fecal material and pathogenic organisms, as well as other human and industrial wastes which have not been properly disposed of. In rural areas, water from small

streams draining isolated or uninhabited watersheds may possess adequate bacteriological and chemical quality for human consumption in its natural state. However, in most instances surface water is subject to pollution and contamination by pathogenic organisms and cannot be considered safe without treatment. It should be remembered that clear water is not necessarily fit for human consumption and that one cannot depend wholly on self-purification to produce portable water (Edmund G. Wagner, 1983).

2. Methods

2.1. Study Area

The Namobuddha Municipality is a newly designated entity under the new Constitution of Nepal, which empowers local government through constitutional provisions and elected representatives. It is a municipality in the Mahabharat mid-hills of the country, just east of Kathmandu Valley, with high ridges, great rivers, and productive mountain flanks and valleys. The population of the municipality is 29,519, made up primarily of the Tamang ethnic community and the Parbate hill community. Namobuddha Municipality is one of six designated ‘urban municipalities’ of Kavre Districts and lies adjacent to the Dhulikhel and Panauti towns as well as the Panchkhal Valley. The main sources of drinking water are natural ponds, wells, and public taps. There are other surface water sources available for collecting water. No information on wastewater treatment facility was found for this particular

Fig.1. The project study area (Namobuddha Municipality)

2.2. Treatment Unit and Process

Water treatment is any process that improves the quality of water to make it appropriate for a specific end-use. The end use may be drinking, industrial water supply, irrigation, river flow maintenance, water recreation, or many other uses, including being safely returned to the environment. Water treatment removes contaminants and undesirable components or reduces their concentration so that the water becomes fit for its desired end-use.

This treatment is crucial to human health and allows humans to benefit from both drinking and irrigation use (Wikipedia, 2020)

2.2.1. Water treatment processes

Water treatment processes are applied to surface water sources. Typically, a water treatment plant (WTP) comprises intake, pumping, pre-sedimentation (in some cases), coagulation, flocculation, clarification, adsorption, filtration, disinfection, storage, and pumping to treat water for consumption as shown in the figure below. When designing water treatment facilities, the main factors to be considered are the type of water source, finished water quality, the skill of facility operators, and the available size of funds.

2.2.2. Water Demand

Total population of Namobudhha Municipality, 2068 = 29,591 (Municipal Profile, 2068)

2.2.3. Population projection

Logistic Population Model: Minarul Haque et al., 2012 used the formula $P_t = P_o * e^{(r+k)t}$

Where, P_o = current population

P_t = population after time t

r = growth rate and

k = annual migration rate.

But for the small population, we may use the discrete model as $P_t = P_o * (1+r)^t$

Table 2.1 (Source: (Nepal Population Growth Rate 1950-2021 | MacroTrends,))

Year	Growth rate	Projected Population
2068	-	29,591
2069	-0.19	29,534
2070	-0.27	29,455
2071	-0.04	29,443
2072	+0.41	29,563
2073	+0.92	29,835
2074	+1.35	30,238
2075	+1.68	30,746
2076	+1.83	31,309
2077	+1.85	31,888
2078	+1.85	32,478

Take **Design population** = 33,000

2.2.4. Peak Factor

Using Harmon's Formula (Qasim & Zhu, 2017),

Peak factor (PF) = $1 + \frac{14}{4 + \sqrt{P}}$ where P is in thousands

$$= 1 + \frac{14}{4 + \sqrt{33}}$$

$$= 3.07$$

Average water consumption = 100 L/capita/day (Source: Dr. Chris Hold, Northampton University)

Average discharge, $Q_{avg} = 26,000 \text{ cap.} * 100 \text{ L/capita/day}$

$$= 26,00,000 \text{ L/day}$$

$$= 2600 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$$

$$= 0.030 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$$

Take $Q_{avg} = 0.040 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$

Peak discharge, $Q_{peak} = Q_{avg} * PF$

$$= 0.040 * 2.54$$

$$= 0.1016 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$$

Take $Q_{peak} = 0.12 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$

3. Water Quality

“Water quality” is a term used here to express the suitability of water to sustain various uses or processes. Any particular user will have certain requirements for the physical, chemical, or biological characteristics of water; for example, limits on the concentrations of toxic substances for drinking water use, or restrictions on temperature and pH ranges for water supporting invertebrate communities (M. Meybeck, 1996).

All potable water systems regulated by the Regional Health Authorities are required to meet the provincial Drinking Water Protection Regulations under the Drinking Water Protection Act and shall meet or exceed Health Guidelines for Drinking Water Quality. In general, these standards require that water supplies for drinking, culinary and other domestic uses be free of pathogenic organisms and their indicators, and free of deleterious chemical substances including radioactive materials. In addition, the water should not have an objectionable color, odor, or taste and should be neither unduly corrosive nor unduly encrusting (BC Ministry of Health, 2012).

Water quality parameters, such as pH, electrical conductivity (EC), total dissolved salts (TDS), chloride (Cl⁻), alkalinity, Ca⁺⁺, Na⁺, K⁺, Mg⁺⁺, nitrate (NO₃), and SO₄, turbidity, and hardness should remain within the allowable limits recommended by Nepal standard as shown in Table 3.1 (Aziz & Mustafa, 2019).

Table 3.1: Drinking Water Quality Standards, Nepal

Group	Parameter	Unit	Maximum Concentration Limits
Physical and chemicals	Turbidity	NTU	5 (10)**
	pH		6.5-8.5*
	Color	TCU	5 (15)**
	Taste & Odor		Would not be objectionable
	Total Dissolved Solids	mg/l	1000
	Electrical Conductivity	µc/cm	1500
	Iron	mg/l	0.3 (3)**
	Manganese	mg/l	0.2
	Arsenic	mg/l	0.05
	Cadmium	mg/l	0.003
	Chromium	mg/l	0.05
	Cyanide	mg/l	0.07
	Fluoride	mg/l	0.5-1.5*
	Lead	mg/l	0.01
	Ammonia	mg/l	1.5
	Chloride	mg/l	250
	Sulphate	mg/l	250
	Nitrate	mg/l	50
	Copper	mg/l	1
	Total Hardness	mg/l	500
Calcium	mg/l	200	
Zinc	mg/l	3	
Mercury	mg/l	0.001	
Aluminum	mg/l	0.2	
Residual Chlorine	mg/l	0.1-0.2*	
Micro Germs	E-Coli	MPN/100ml	0
	Total Coli form	MPN/100ml	95 % in sample

Note : * These standards indicate the maximum and minimum limits.

** Figures in parenthesis are upper range of the standards recommended.

3.1. Water quantity

Table 3.1.1 Quantity of river water (Aziz & Mustafa, 2019)

	Average Discharge (m ³ /s)											
	Jan.	Feb.	Mar.	Apr.	May	Jun.	Jul.	Aug.	Sept.	Oct.	Nov.	Dec.
2001	*N.R	N.R	N.R	N.R	N.R	N.R	N.R	N.R	57	59	70	309
2002	223	222	394	1047	859	500	294	106	87	85	87	259
2003	242	352	N.R	N.R	N.R	380	193	N.R	N.R	N.R	N.R	121
2004	392	401	826	658	674	666	340	114	74	72	80	171
2005	481	767	1033	842	644	560	327	108	72	73	80	127
2006	366	1182	987	933	733	587	302	155	140	152	262	191
2007	335	756	742	728	708	445	240	124	100	95	101	119
2008	98	157	343	324	235	153	89	67	58	75	77	85
2009	104	132	384	433	486	275	141	84	74	71	174	194
2010	304	334	439	471	503	317	178	124	102	80	72	75
2011	90	203	324	613	622	391	227	143	120	117	124	120
2012	142	206	282	563	513	248	155	119	106	111	140	144
2013	398	505	540	581	535	402	368	210	185	177	190	225
2014	242	250	412	393	338	239	182	154	138	202	233	265
2015	247	253	305	435	407	260	181	149	140	166	211	197
2016	408	341	535	582	498	318	202	151	135	129	138	178
2017	164	176	325	578	483	N.R	N.R	N.R	N.R	N.R	N.R	N.R

*N.R. means non recorded data

4. Intake

The basic function of the intake structure is to help safely withdraw water from the water source and to discharge this water into the withdrawal conduit (normally called intake conduit) through which it flows up to a WTP. The water is diverted through a raw water gravity pipe into the wet well (intake) (Aziz & Mustafa, 2019a).

4.1. Screening design

It is done for the removal of coarse solids (floating objects, wood, papers, rags, plastics, leaves, etc.) from river water.

We all know,

$$Q_{\text{avg}} = 0.040 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$$

For the manually cleaned screen design,

- Design Criteria of a Bar Screen:**
- Approach Velocity**
- Optimum Velocity: 0.6 m/s (through the screen opening)**
- Maximum Velocity: 0.75-1.0 m/s (to prevent entrapped materials being forced through the bars).**
- Minimum Velocity: 0.4 m/s to prevent deposition of solids.**
- Typical Range: 0.6-10 m/s**
- Head loss:**
- $h_L=0.05-0.15$ m for drinking water.**
- $h_L=0.10-0.40$ m for sewage (wastewater)**
- Cleaning Mechanism: Manual mechanism**
- The angle of inclination (10-60)**

Source: (Qasim & Zhu, 2017)

4.1.1. Design of channel

Cross-section of the channel,

$$A_c = Q_d / V_a$$

Where V_a is the maximum velocity assumed to be 0.6 m/s and Q_d is the design discharge

$$\begin{aligned} A_c &= (0.040 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}) / (0.6 \frac{\text{m}}{\text{s}}) \\ &= 0.067 \text{ m}^2 \end{aligned}$$

Let us consider rectangular coarse screen in **Depth: Width ratio 1.5: 1** (Source: (Qasim & Zhu, 2017))

$$\text{Then, the width of the channel} = \sqrt{\frac{0.067}{1.5}} = 0.211 \text{ m}$$

Take width = 0.220 m

depth of channel = $1.5 * 0.220 = 0.330$ m

4.1.2. Design of bar screen

Consider bar screen aligning 60 degrees to the horizontal i.e., inclination angle of the screen.

Area of bar screen = $0.067 / \sin 60^\circ$ (Source: (Qasim & Zhu, 2017))

$$= 0.077 \text{ m}^2$$

Consider space between bars = 4 cm

Thickness of the bar screens = 10 mm

Calculating $A_{\text{net}} = 0.077 * \frac{4}{4+1} = 0.061 \text{ m}^2$

Take $A_{\text{net}} = 0.070 \text{ m}^2$

Checking, using continuity equation;

$$V_a * A_c = V_o * A_{\text{net}}$$

$$V_o = 0.6 * 0.067 / 0.070 = 0.57 \text{ m}$$

Which is less than the maximum approach velocity for the design of bar screen 0.9 m/s. **Hence OK!**

For the number of bars,

From the above formula,

$$n * 10 \text{ mm} + (n + 1) * 4 \text{ cm} = 0.22 \text{ m}$$

$$0.01n + 0.04n + 0.04 = 0.22$$

$$n = 3.6$$

So, 4 bars are taken.

4.1.3 Head Loss

Similarly, calculating head loss,

$$\Delta H \text{ or } h_L = \beta \left[\frac{W}{S} \right]^{\frac{4}{3}} \left[\frac{V_a^2}{2g} \right] \sin \theta$$

W	:	Maximum width of the bar (m)
S	:	Minimum aperture (clear spacing of the bars)
V _a	:	approach velocity in upstream channel (m/s)
β	:	Bar shape factor (β =2.42 for sharp edge or rectangular and 1.79 for circular)
θ	:	Angle of inclination of the bar to the horizontal

$$\Delta H = 2.42 * \left(\frac{0.220 \text{ m}}{4 \text{ cm}} \right)^{\frac{4}{3}} * \left(\frac{0.6^2}{2 * 9.81} \right) * \sin 60$$

$$\Delta H = 0.373 \text{ m}$$

The actual head loss through a clean screen may be between 0.370 and 0.375 m.

Design criteria of a bar screen

Head lose

❑ **h_l = 0.05-0.15 m for drinking water**

❑ **h_l = 0.10-0.40 m for sewage (Wastewater)** Source: (Qasim & Zhu, 2017)

My calculation of head loss doesn't lie within the design criteria of drinking water so on increasing the design discharge, the width of the channel used in coarse increases thus decreases the heat loss from the screening process.

Note: We will place coarse screens before collection tanks after the water is brought from the river.

4.1.4. Design of intake tank

The average discharge (Q_{avg}) used in the design of the intake is described as follows:

$$Q_{\text{avg}} = 0.040 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$$

I will provide only **one pipe** to convey water.

Let's assume velocity inside the gravity pipe = 0.6 m/s (**Hit and Trial**)

$$\text{Area (A)} = \text{Discharge (Q)} / \text{velocity (v)}$$

$$= 0.040 / 0.6$$

$$\frac{\pi * d^2}{4} = 0.067 \text{ m}^2$$

Thus, Diameter of pipe = 0.292 m

Take 300 mm pipe

Suppose one circular tank to fill up the intake

detention time (t) = 20 minutes (**Assumption**)

Volume of tank = discharge * detention time

$$= 0.040 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec} * 20 \text{ minute}$$

$$= 48 \text{ m}^3$$

Take effective depth of the tank = 10 m

Area of the tank = $48 / 10 = 4.8 \text{ m}^2$

Therefore, diameter of the tank = $\sqrt{\frac{4*4.8}{\pi}} = 2.47 \text{ m}$

Take the diameter of tank = 2.50 m

Plan of the Intake

The design of the suction pipe is as follows:

$$Q = 0.040 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec}$$

v = 1.5 m/s (**Assumption**)

The cross-sectional area of the suction pipe is;

$$A = Q / v$$

$$= 0.040 / 1.5$$

$$= 0.027 \text{ m}^2$$

Diameter of suction pipe = $\sqrt{\frac{4*0.027}{\pi}} = 0.185 \text{ m}$

Use d = 0.200 m

Note: Here water from the Roshi river is sucked through a suction pipe and then transport in a tank before treatment. Till now, no treatment process is executed.

5. Pre-Sedimentation

Sedimentation is recommended as a simple and low-cost pre-treatment of water before application of other purification treatments such as filtration and disinfection methods. It removes undesirable small particulate suspended matters (sand, silt, and clay) and some biological contaminants from water under the influence of gravity. It also improves the visual qualities of the water and increases its acceptance by consumers. The longer

the water is sediment, the more the suspended solids and pathogens will settle to the bottom of the container. Sedimentation is low-cost pre-treatment technology to reduce settleable solids and some microbes from water under the influence of gravity before the application of other purification methods. It also improves the visual qualities of the water and increases its acceptance by consumers (Taghizadeh, 2018).

The purpose of a primary sedimentation basin is to remove settleable organic solids. It is achieved in large basins under relatively quiescent conditions. The settled solids are collected by mechanical scrapers into a hopper, from which they are pumped to a sludge processing area. Oil, grease, and other floating materials are skimmed off from the surface. The effluent is discharged over weirs into a collection trough (Qasim & Zhu, 2017).

Commonly, pre-sedimentation without coagulant addition or a roughing filter is used to remove high concentrations of settleable solids before coagulation-flocculation- sedimentation.

5.1.1 Coagulation

Often chemicals are added to enhance the removal efficiency of a plain sedimentation basin. The colloidal particles are flocculated and removed with the settling floc. These particles would otherwise not be removed in plain sedimentation. Chemicals may also be added to precipitate soluble organics, phosphorous, and heavy metals, the process is called coagulation (Qasim & Zhu, 2017).

Chemical Coagulation includes all of the reactions and mechanisms involved in the chemical destabilization of particles and the formation of larger particles through peri kinetic flocculation (aggregation of particles in the size range from 0.001 to 1 micron). A coagulant is a chemical that is added to destabilize the colloidal particles in water and wastewater so that floc formation can result. Typical coagulants include natural and synthetic organic polymers, metal salts such as alum or ferric chloride, and prehydrolyzed metal salts such as poly aluminum chloride (PACI), polyiron chloride (PICI), and Polydiallyldimethylammonium chloride (polyDADMAC).

5.1.2. Design of coagulant tank

$$Q_{avg} = 0.040 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec} = 2.4 \text{ m}^3/\text{min}$$

Let's suppose the quantity of water lost during desludging = 2%

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Total discharge } Q_{avg} &= 2.4 \text{ m}^3/\text{min} + 0.02 * 2.4 \text{ m}^3/\text{min} \\ &= 2.45 \text{ m}^3/\text{min} \end{aligned}$$

Suppose expected removal efficiency of minimum size particles (y/y_o) = 80%

Minimum diameter of particles to be removed = 0.8 mm

For the settling velocity,

$$V_s = \frac{g}{18} * \frac{(s - 1)d^2}{\vartheta}$$

where,

s = specific gravity of particles = 1.002

d = diameter of particles to be removed = 0.8 mm

ϑ = Kinematic viscosity of water at 20°C = 1.01×10^{-6} m²/s

Acceleration due to gravity, g = 9.81 m/s²

$$V_s = 9.81 / 18 * (1.002 - 1) * (0.8 * 10^{-3})^2 / (1.01 \times 10^{-6}) = 6.90 * 10^{-4} \text{ m/s}$$

Check for Reynolds Number,

$$Re = V_s * d / \vartheta$$

$$= \frac{6.90 * 10^{-4} * 0.8 * 10^{-3}}{1.01 \times 10^{-6}}$$

= 0.546 < 1 satisfies Stoke's law condition for laminar flow.

For surface overflow rate,

$$v_s = v_o$$

$$v_o = \frac{6.90 * 10^{-4} \text{ m}}{\text{s}} * 60 * 60 * \frac{24 \text{ s}}{\text{day}}$$

$$v_o = 59.616 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$$

To overcome the short-circuiting and to achieve the desired efficiency,

$$\frac{y}{y_o} = \left[1 - \left(1 + n \frac{v_o}{Q/A} \right)^{-\frac{1}{n}} \right]$$

Here, y = particles removed, y_o = initial concentration of particles.

$$\frac{v_o}{Q/A} = \frac{1}{n} \left[\left(1 - \frac{y}{y_o} \right)^{-n} - 1 \right]$$

where, n is the Assumed performance of the settling tank to be n = 1/8

$$= 1 / 0.125 * ((1 - 0.8)^{-0.125} - 1)$$

$$= 1.78$$

$$\frac{Q}{A} = \frac{v_o}{1.78} = 33.49 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^2/\text{day}$$

Which lies within the range of 30-40 m³/m²/day

Using **one paddle mixer**;

Take detention time of 1 minute (**Assumption:**)

$$\text{Volume of mixer} = Q * t = 2.4 * 1 = 2.4 \text{ m}^3$$

Suppose depth of tank = 3 m

$$\text{Area of tank} = 2.4 / 3 = 0.8 \text{ m}^2$$

Using circular tank,

$$\text{Diameter of tank} = \sqrt{\frac{4 * 0.8}{\pi}} = 1.009 \text{ m}$$

Use diameter of tank = 1.2m

Calculating Power in a mechanical paddle system

At room temperature T = 25 °C, dynamic viscosity ($\mu = 0.890 \times 10^{-3}$ Pa.s) (Source: (Qasim & Zhu, 2017); Appendix B, Table B2)

For horizontal flow mixing,

Velocity gradient, G = 1000 /s (Range: 500-2500) (Source: (Eddy, 2014))

$$V = 2.4 \text{ m}^3$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} P &= G^2 * \mu * V \\ &= 1000^2 * 0.890 \times 10^{-3} * 2.4 \\ &= 2136 \text{ Watt} \\ &= 2.136 \text{ kW} \end{aligned}$$

5.1.2. Amount of the coagulant

To determine the amount of the coagulant (e.g., alum) required per day (kg/day), I used the optimum dosage of alum at 25 mg/L (normally optimum dosage determined by Jar test), and I supposed that the density of alum was 600 kg/m³.

$$Q = 0.040 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec} = 0.040 * 24 * 60 * 60 \text{ m}^3/\text{day} = 3456 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$$

$$\text{Amount of alum} = \frac{25 \text{ mg}}{\text{l}} * \frac{1000 \text{ l}}{\text{m}^3} * \frac{1 \text{ kg}}{1000 * 1000 \text{ mg}} * \frac{3456 \text{ m}^3}{\text{day}}$$

$$= 86.4 \text{ kg/day}$$

$$\text{Volume of alum} = \text{mass of alum} / \text{density of alum}$$

$$= 0.144 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$$

$$= 4.32 \text{ m}^3/\text{month}$$

6. Flocculation

Flocculation is the process of slow mixing that can be achieved in a basin, which is known as a flocculator. It is an essential operation designed to agitate force in fluid and coagulation. Flocculation term is used to describe the process whereby the size of particles increases as a result of particle collisions. A flocculant is a chemical, typically organic, added to enhance the flocculation process.

Design of flocculant tank

$$Q_{\text{avg}} = 0.040 \text{ m}^3/\text{sec} = 2.4 \text{ m}^3/\text{min}$$

Take detention time of 30 minute

$$\text{Volume of mixer} = Q * t = 2.4 * 30 = 72 \text{ m}^3$$

Use two parallel tanks,

$$\text{Discharge in 1 tank} = 72 \text{ m}^3 / 2 = 36 \text{ m}^3$$

Suppose depth of tank = 4 m

$$\text{Area of tank} = 36 / 4 = 9 \text{ m}^2$$

Using circular tank,

$$\text{Diameter of tank} = \sqrt{\frac{4 * 9}{\pi}} = 3.385 \text{ m}$$

Use diameter of tank = 3.40 m

7. Clarification

Sedimentation, also known as settling or clarification, is the process of removing solid particles by gravity. To design a clarification tank,

Design of sedimentation tank

Surface Area Calculation:

Surface area of the tank is calculated through the formula:

$$\text{Surface Area (A)} = \frac{Q_{\text{avg}}}{OA}$$

$$A = \frac{3456}{32} = 108 \text{ m}^2$$

Where, Q_{avg} = Average flow rate

OR = Overflow Rate which is $32/\text{m}^3/\text{m}^2 \cdot \text{d}$ at average flow

Length of the Tank:

Tank length is calculated is by using:

$L=A/W$, where W is the channel Width taken as 3m. Two clarifiers are used in this design plant.

$$L=\frac{108}{2*3}=18\text{m. The length of the sedimentation tank is 18m}$$

Detention time and overflow rate at an average flow

Using the assumed side water depth of 4 m,

$$\text{Tank volume} = 4\text{m} * 2(18\text{m} * 3\text{m}) = 432 \text{ m}^3$$

$$\text{Overflow rate} = Q/A = \frac{3456}{2(3*18)} = 32 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^2.\text{d}$$

$$\text{Detention time} = V/Q = \frac{432*24}{3456} = 3.0\text{h}$$

Detention time and overflow rate at peak flow.

$$\text{Overflow rate} = Q/A = \frac{8586}{2(3*18)} = 80 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^2.\text{d}$$

$$\text{Detention time} = V/Q = \frac{432*24}{8586} = 1.2 \text{ h}$$

Scour velocity

We use the following values to calculate scour velocity. Source: (Metcalf and Eddy, 2003)

Cohesion constant: $k = 0.05$

Specific Gravity: $s = 1.25$

Acceleration due to gravity: $g = 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2$

Diameter of particles: $d = 100 * 10^{-6} \text{ m}$

Darcy – Weibach friction factor: $f = 0.025$

$$V_{\text{scour}} = \left[\frac{8k(s-1)gd}{f} \right]^{1/2} = \left[\frac{8*0.05*0.25*9.81*100}{0.025*1000000} \right]^{1/2} = 0.063 \text{ m/s}$$

Horizontal velocity through the settling tank.

$V_{\text{horizontal}} = Q/A_c$, where A_c is the cross-sectional area through which the flow passes.

$$= \frac{8586}{2*(3*4)*80*3600} = 0.009 \text{ m/s}$$

The horizontal velocity, even at peak flow, is substantially less than the scour velocity. Therefore, the settled matter should not be resuspended.

BOD and TSS removal at average and peak flow.

a. At average flow:

$$\text{TSS removal} = \frac{t}{a+bt} = \frac{3}{0.0075+(0.014)(3)} = 60.60 \%$$

$$\text{BOD removal} = \frac{t}{a+bt} = \frac{3}{0.018+(0.020)(3)} = 38.46 \%$$

b. At peak flow:

$$\text{BOD removal} = \frac{t}{a+bt} = \frac{1.2}{0.018+(0.020)(1.2)} = 28.57 \%$$

$$\text{TSS removal} = \frac{t}{a+bt} = \frac{1.2}{0.0075+(0.014)(1.2)} = 49.38 \%$$

Effluent troughs with weir plates

The total length of effluent weir required at the design weir loading rate of $125 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}\cdot\text{d}$.

$$L_{\text{total}} = \frac{8568}{125} = 68.54 \text{ m}$$

Calculate the total number of weir plates required at a length of effluent weir plate $L_{\text{plate}} = 3 \text{ m/plate}$.

$$N_{\text{plate}} = L_{\text{total}}/L_{\text{plate}} = \frac{68.54}{3} = 22.848 = 23 \text{ weir plates}$$

Provide 14 troughs (N launder = 14 launders) with weir plates on both sides of the trough.

Total number of 90° V-notches

The head over a V-notch is calculated from the equation.

$$q = \frac{8}{15}C_d(2g)^{1/2}\tan\frac{\theta}{2}H^{5/2}$$

where,

q = flow per notch, m^3/s (ft^3/s)

C_d = coefficient of discharge

A C_d of 0.6 is typically used for a V-notch.

θ = angle of the V-notch, degree

H = head over the V-notch, m

For a 90° V-notch, $\theta = 90^\circ$, and $\tan(\theta/2) = \tan(90^\circ/2) = \tan(45^\circ) = 1$

$$\text{Therefore, } q = \frac{8}{15}C_d(2g)^{1/2}H^{5/2}$$

Provide notches 20-cm center-to-center and from each end of the weir plate to the center of the nearest V-notch.

The number of 90° V-notches on each weir plate at $L_{\text{space}} = 0.20 \text{ m}$.

$$N_{\text{notches/plate}} = (L_{\text{plate}}/L_{\text{space}}) - 1 = (3 \text{ m/plate}/0.20 \text{ m}) - 1 = 14 \text{ notches/plate.}$$

The total number of 90° V-notches.

$$N_{\text{notch}} = N_{\text{plate}} \times N_{\text{notch/plate}} = 23 \text{ weir plates} \times 14 \text{ notches/plate} = 322 \text{ notches}$$

Flow per 90° V-notch at design flow of 0.289 m³/s.

$$q = Q / N_{\text{notch}} = 0.28/322 = 0.00086 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$$

Head over 90° V-notch

$$H = 0.034 \text{ m}$$

Depth of effluent launders

Flow per launder.

$$Q_{\text{launder}} = Q / N_{\text{launder}} = 0.289/14 = 0.0206 \text{ m}^3/\text{s}$$

Critical depth

$$y_c = (Q_{\text{launder}}^2 / gb^2)^{1/3} \text{ where } b \text{ is the width of launder, } b = 0.45 \text{ and } C_w = 1$$
$$= \left(\frac{0.000424}{0.2025 * 9.8} \right)^{1/3} = 0.05 \text{ m}$$

For a free fall into the effluent exit channel, assume the water depth $y_2 = y_c = 0.17 \text{ m}$ at the lower end of the launder.

The water depth y_1 at the upper end of the launder

$$y_1 = (y_2^2 + (2Q_{\text{launder}}^2) / gb^2 y_2)^{1/2} = 0.07 \text{ m}$$

Add 10% additional depth for friction and turbulence losses. Total water depth at the upper end = $1.1 \times 0.07 \text{ m} = 0.086 \text{ m}$ Add the height of 0.20 m for free fall below the V-notches, the head of 0.05 m over the V-notches, the freeboard of 0.03 m above the head at the notches, and the additional freeboard of 0.10 m above the weir plate to the top of the launder. Total depth of effluent launder = $(0.086 + 0.20 + 0.05 + 0.03 + 0.10) \text{ m} = 0.46 \text{ m}$

Filtration aims to remove the suspended solids that are not removed in the sedimentation unit or when the removal of these particles takes a long time outside the basin.

Design Criteria of Horizontal Roughing Filter

Drain time (T) - 1 to 2 minutes

Rate of filtration, (VF) - 0.30 m/hr to 1.50 m/hr

Drainage velocity, (vd) - 60 to 90 m/hr

Diameter of the drain pipe, (ddp) - 150 to 200 mm

Diameter of the perforation drain pipe, (dhdp) - 6 to 10 mm

Spacing of perforation in the drain pipe, (shdp) - 0.5 to 1.0 m

Diameter of perforation of dividing wall, (dpf) - 40 mm

Area of perforation on dividing wall (Apf) - 25% of the surface area of the filter

The volume of voids in filter media - 50%

Partial head loss, ΔH - 0.15 m

Filter media - 4 to 8 mm, 8 to 12 mm, and 12 to 18 mm

Depth of filter media - 0.8 to 1.2 m

Length filter, 1st chamber (L1) - 2 to 4 m

2nd chamber (L2) - 1 to 3 m

3rd chamber (L3) - 1 to 2 m

Let's assume that the pre-settled raw water is of medium turbidity and the applied filtration rates should range between 0.75 and 1 m/h. For this relatively high turbidity, take a filtration rate of 0.75 m/h.

The HRF units are of the following dimensions:

Final design capacity: $Q = 162 \text{ m}^3/\text{d} = 6.75 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$

$$V_F = 0.75 \text{ m/h}$$

Cross-sectional area:

Required cross-sectional area for $6.75 \text{ m}^3/\text{h} = 6.75/0.75 = 9 \text{ m}^2$

Assumption: 3 HRF units

Filter depth $H = 1.2 \text{ m}$

Filter width $W = 2.4 \text{ m}$

Filter length/gravel size $L1 = 4\text{m}, d_g = 15 \text{ mm}$

$L2 = 2\text{m}, d_g = 10 \text{ mm}$

$L3 = 1\text{m}, d_g = 5 \text{ mm}$

Total filter length $L = 7 \text{ m}$

Designed filtration rate:

$$V_F = \frac{6.75}{3 \times 1.2 \times 2.4} = 0.78 \text{ m/h}$$

Filtration rate $V_F = 0.75 \text{ m/h}$

	E-value(%)
Gravel size 15 mm, Filter length 4m	15.2
Gravel size 10 mm, Filter length 2m	25.7
Gravel size 5 mm, Filter length 1 m	28.3

Hence, for an assumed maximum suspended solids concentration of 300 mg/L in the pre-settled raw water, the respective concentration $1n$ the HRF amounts to:

$$C_e = 300 * 0.152 * 0.257 * 0.283 = 3.3 \text{ mg/L}$$

The time interval between two cleanings:

With an assumed average suspended solids concentration of 200 mg/L in the pre-settled water and a maximum allowable filter load of 10 g/L in the first gravel pack, the filter running time between two hydraulic cleanings amounts to:

$$T_{\text{run}} = 1000 \frac{\sigma L 1}{(C_o - C_e) v_f} \quad \text{where } T_{\text{run}} \text{ (h) time interval between two cleanings}$$

σ (g/L) average filter load

L , (m) filter length of the first filter fraction

C_o , C_e (mg/L) susp. solids conc. at the beginning and the end

of the first filter fraction

V_f (m/h) filtration rate

$$T_{\text{run}} = 1000 * \frac{10 * 4}{(200 - 30) * 0.75} = 310 \text{ hrs} = 13 \text{ days}$$

with $C_e = 200 * 0.152 = 30$ mg/l (susp. Solids conc after the first gravel pack)

9. Adsorption

Activated carbon is used to remove colors and tastes in water, resulting in the presence of dissolved gases. It is also porous and has many carbon atoms with free valencies. In addition, it is available in granular or powder form. Granular activated carbon has a surface area of 500–1400 m² /g. (Metcalf & Eddy, 2014). Activated carbon can be applied to treat water in two ways: As powder feed (during adding alum to mixing basin or after coagulation) As filter media, instead of sand filter bed (McGhee, 1991).

Adsorption isotherm is a mathematical model that describes the distribution of adsorbate species among liquid and adsorbent based on the assumptions of heterogeneity/homogeneity of adsorbents. Adsorption data are described by Langmuir or Freundlich adsorption isotherms.

9.1 Langmuir isotherm

This model is based on the assumption that maximum adsorption occurs when a saturated monolayer of solute molecules is present on the adsorbent surface. The energy of adsorption is constant, and adsorbate molecules do not migrate on the surface plane (Amin, 2018). The Langmuir isothermal equation is stated as follows:

$$q_e = (q_m K_L C_e) / (1 + K_L C_e)$$

The constants of the Langmuir isotherm can be determined by plotting $(1/q_e)$ versus $(1/C_e)$, and the above equation is rewritten as follows:

$$1/q_e = 1/q_m + (1/q_m K_L)(1/C_e)$$

Where

q_e refers to the weight of adsorbate (g)

q_m is the Langmuir constant (mg/g)

K_L is the Langmuir constant (L/mg)

C_e is the equilibrium concentration of adsorbate (mg/L).

9.1.2 Freundlich isotherm

This model is an empirical relationship describing the adsorption of solutes from a liquid to a solid surface and assumes that different sites with several adsorption energies are involved (Amin,2018). The equation is as follows:

$$q_e = K_f C_e^{(1/n)}$$

The equation in the form of logarithm becomes:

$$\text{Log} = \log K_f + 1/2 \log C_e$$

where (Kf) and (n) are Freundlich constants, the characteristics of the system. The settled water in the laboratory should be subjected to kinetic analysis to determine the optimum dosage of the adsorbent.

10. Backwashing and Disinfection

In terms of water treatment, including water purification and sewage treatment, backwashing refers to pumping water backward through the filter's media, sometimes including intermittent use of compressed air during the process. Backwashing is a form of preventive maintenance so that the filter media can be reused. In water treatment plants, backwashing can be an automated process that is run by local programmable logic controllers (PLCs). The backwash cycle is triggered after a set time interval, when the filter effluent turbidity is greater than a treatment guideline or when the differential pressure (head loss) across the filter exceeds a set value.

The amount of backwashing water should be less than or equal to the 5% rate of filtered water (Aziz & Mustafa, 2019b).

$$\text{Rate of wash water} = \text{filtration rate} = VF = 5 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^2/\text{h}$$

Since I have used only one filter unit.

$$Q_{\text{backwash}} = 0.05 * 5 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^2/\text{h} = 0.25 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^2/\text{h}$$

$$\text{Wash area} = 33.10 \text{ m}^2$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Amount of water needed for washing} &= 33.10 \text{ m}^2 * 5 \text{ m}^3/\text{m}^2/\text{h} \\ &= 165.5 \text{ m}^3/\text{h} \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Suppose Head of wash water} = 10 \text{ m and Frictional resistance} = 4 \text{ m}$$

$$\text{Total head required} = 10 + 4 = 14 \text{ m}$$

10.1 Disinfection

When the filtered water comes out from the filter unit, bacteria and other microorganisms, which may be pathogenic, may exist. Thus, disinfection is necessary to eliminate bacteria and other microorganisms and consequently prevent waterborne diseases. Disinfection involves several methods. The use of chlorine has become particularly common in disinfecting water. It is inexpensive, reliable, and relatively safe to handle (Punmia et al., 1996).

Water demand = 3456 m³ /day

Required chlorine and residual chlorine are 0.36 and 0.2 mg/L, respectively (Punmia et al.,1996).

Chlorine demand = 0.36 mg/L – 0.2 mg/L = 0.16 mg/L

Consumed chlorine = 0.36 mg/L × (1/ 10⁶) × 3456 × 1000 = 1.24 kg/day

The time required to complete the disinfection performed in a storage tank is 0.5 h (McGhee,1991).

$Q = \text{Volume} / \text{time}$

$\text{Volume} = Q \times \text{time}$

$\text{Volume} = 3456 \text{ m}^3 / \text{day} \times (1/24) \times 0.5 \text{ h} = 72 \text{ m}^3$

Using effective depth of 4 m and length (L) = 2× width (W)

$A = 72 \text{ m}^3 / 4 \text{ m} = 28 \text{ m}^2$

$L \times W = 18 \text{ m}^2$

$2 W \times W = 18 \text{ m}^2$

$W^2 = 9 \text{ m}^2$

$W = 3. \text{ m}$ and $L = 2 \times 3 = 6 \text{ m}$

$\text{Velocity} = \text{distance} / \text{time}$

$\text{Velocity} = 6 \text{ m} / 0.5 \text{ h} = 12 \text{ m/h} = 0.003 \text{ m/s}$

11.Storage and pumping

When the final stages of the treatment process are completed, water can be distributed by high lift pumps to consumers or stored in storage tanks. There are 2 storage tanks in this treatment plant. One tank is always full while another tank is empty for maintenance and cleaning purposes. Two pumps are used one as a backup and another functioning.

12. Conclusion

A step-by-step design for WTP units was presented in this study. Procedures, detailed calculations, and drawings were illustrated. The average discharge of 3456 m³/day and a population of 32,478 were used in the design of WTP. The outputs of the calculations and the details of the WTP units were tabulated. The quality and quantity of the surface water source affected the WTP design. Surface water resource from Roshi river was treated using various process and techniques. The parameters of each unit and the whole WTP by using the pilot-scale should be optimized. Populations should be predicted using various methods to use WTP services without any problems. Based on the obtained calculations and details it is concluded that the study can be used as a base reference for future works and to the design of any WTP. Through calculation and study, a suitable treatment plant was designed for to levels that meet and Nepal standards for consumption.

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